

successively with water, aqueous sodium carbonate (10%), water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and filtered. It was then concentrated when light yellow crystals separated, m.p. 247-49° (0.15 g).

Method II: III (0.2 g) was taken in a hard glass test tube and heated with polyphosphoric acid (4 g) on a glycerol bath at 140° for 1 h. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and the solid separated was filtered and washed. The crude product was suspended in aqueous sodium carbonate and allowed to stand for 0.5 h. It was filtered, washed and crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 248-49° (0.075 g).

6'-Methoxy-1'-oxo-1H-indeno-(2',3':3,4)-isocoumarin: A solution of IV (0.2 g) in acetone (15 ml) was mixed with dry methyl iodide (5 ml) and anhyd. pot. carbonate (0.15 g). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h and filtered hot. The solvent was evaporated and the product crystallised in ethyl acetate as colourless needles, m.p. 225-27°. IR: 2970, 1710, 1605, 1510 cm^{-1} .

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Synthesis of 1-Arylpiperazine Mannich Bases and Amides of Ethyl 7-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetate as Possible Antiinflammatory Agents

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COUMARIN ring has an easy accessibility in the biological systems as compared to the isomeric-isosteric chromone nucleus¹. Mannich bases of 7-hydroxycoumarins (umbelliferone derivatives) possess profound CNS stimulant activity²⁻¹⁰. In this case, the nature of the amine used as well as that of the substituents on the coumarin moiety have marked effect on the activity. Encouraging results obtained by us in the case of Mannich bases of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with 1-arylpiperazine¹⁰ prompted us to undertake a parallel study

on the analogous Mannich bases of ethyl 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetate (I). Using 1-arylpiperazines (II), Mannich bases (III) of I were prepared. As a further modification, 1-arylpiperazine amides of 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid were also prepared by condensing I with II. These amides (IV) were expected to possess antiinflammatory activity in addition to the CNS activity.

I reacted with II in presence of paraformaldehyde and catalytic amount of KOH in refluxing EtOH to give III. III were characterised as ethyl-8-(4-aryl-1-piperazinylmethyl)-7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetates, based on the previous reports and the spectral data. To locate the position of the piperazinylmethyl residue on the coumarin nucleus, morpholine analogue (V) of III was prepared by a similar method. PMR spectrum (CDCl_3) of V showed two doublets at 6.63 ($J=9\text{Hz}$) and 7.43 ($J=9\text{Hz}$), each integrating for one proton, due to H_5 and H_6 , respectively. Thus, the position of the piperazinylmethyl residue at the 8-position in III was confirmed. To obtain further proof, IIIa was hydrolysed carefully and the resulting carboxylic acid (VI) was decarboxylated to obtain 8-(4-phenyl-1-piperazinylmethyl)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (VII); spectral data for which was consonant with the structure. VII could also be obtained by the reaction of 1-phenylpiperazine with 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, obtained by the condensation of resorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate, in the presence of paraformaldehyde in absolute alcohol. II on heating with excess I gave 7-hydroxy-4-[2-(4-aryl-1-piperazinyl)-2-oxoethyl]coumarins (IV).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA AND ANTIINFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF III

Compd.	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen %* Found (Calcd.)	% Inhibition of edema**
IIIa	H	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅	192-93	60	6.59 (6.63)	25.0
IIIb	2-CH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₅	142-43	43	6.40 (6.42)	3.0
IIIc	3-CH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₅	147-48	51	6.39 (6.42)	20.9
IIIId	4-CH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₅	155-56	57	6.44 (6.42)	19.0
IIIe	2-Cl	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₅	139-40	58	6.12 (6.14)	10.0
IIIf	3-Cl	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₅	152-53	38	6.14 (6.14)	26.6
IIIg	4-Cl	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₅	168-69	55	6.17 (6.14)	16.0

* C and H analyses were found to be satisfactory.

** Phenyl butazone (50 mg/kg in 2% gum acasia) was taken as the standard and showed 48% inhibition compared with control when administered orally. The compounds (100 mg/kg) given orally in 2% gum acasia 1 h before carrageenin were injection and the reading was taken 3 h after carrageenin injection.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were run on a Beckman Acculab-10 spectrophotometer and the values are reported in wavenumbers (cm⁻¹). PMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Spectrospin spectrometer at 80 MHz using TMS as the internal standard and the chemical shift values are reported in ppm (δ). 1-Arylpiperazines were prepared by the condensation of diethanolamine with anilines as described in literature¹¹. 7-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid was prepared by the condensation of resorcinol with acetone dicarboxylic acid according to known method^{12,13} and the acid was esterified to I by the usual method.

Ethyl-7-hydroxy-8-(4-morpholinylmethyl)coumarin-4-acetates (V): Catalytic amount of KOH was dissolved in warm ethanol (25 ml). To the warm solution, paraformaldehyde (600 mg, 0.02 mol) was added and dissolved. Morpholine (1.0 g, 0.012 mol) and I (2.48 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (30 ml) were added to this and the mixture refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated and the separated solid was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 213-214, yield, 2.0 g (62.7%) (Found: C, 62.28; H, 6.10; N, 4.02. Calcd. for C₁₈H₂₁NO₆; C, 62.24; H, 6.09; N, 4.03%). IR (KBr): 1730 (broad, -COOEt and lactonic CO) and 1600 (α,β -unsaturation). PMR (CDCl₃): 1.2 (3H, t, -COOCH₂-CH₃, J=7Hz), 2.7 [4H, t, -N(CH₂-)₂], 3.7 [4H, t, O(CH₂-)₂], 3.96-4.32 (6H, m, 4-CH₂COOEt, -COOCH₂CH₃ and 8-CH₂N<), 5.96 (1H, s, C₈H), 6.63 (1H, d, C₆H, J=9Hz), 7.43 (1H, d, C₆H, J=9Hz) and 8.32 (1H, s, 7-OH exchangeable with D₂O).

Ethyl-8-(4-aryl-1-piperazinylmethyl)-7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetates (III): Catalytic amount of KOH was dissolved in warm ethanol (25 ml). Paraformaldehyde (600 mg, 0.02 mol) was added to the warm solution and dissolved. 1-Arylpiperazine (0.015

mol) and I (2.48 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) were added and the mixture refluxed for 6 h. The solution was cooled and the solid filtered. The mother liquor on concentration gave the second crop. Both the crops were crystallized from absolute alcohol (Table I). IR(KBr) of IIIId: 1730 (-COOEt and lactonic CO). PMR (DMSO-d₆) of IIIId: 1.17 (3H, t, -COOCH₂-CH₃, J=7Hz), 2.21 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.8 [4H, t, -CH₂N(CH₂)₂], 3.16 [4H, t, Ar-N(CH₂)₂], 4.1 (6H, m, 4-CH₂COOEt, 4-CH₂COOCH₂CH₃, 8-CH₂N<), 6.17 (1H, s, C₈H) and 6.7-7.6 (6H, m, ArH).

Preparation of 8-(4-phenyl-1-piperazinylmethyl)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin from IIIa: IIIa (1 g) was heated with 1 N NaOH (20 ml) on a water bath for 2-3 h when the compound practically went into the solution. The solution was cooled and neutralised carefully when 8-(4-phenyl-1-piperazinylmethyl)-7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (VI) separated out, (70%). VI (1 g) was heated to its fusion temp and held there for 0.5 h. The mass was cooled and washed thoroughly with NaHCO₃. The residue was crystallised from ab. alcohol, m.p. 220-22°, yield 0.6 g. IR(KBr): 1722 (lactonic CO). PMR(CDCl₃): 2.4 (3H, s, 4-CH₃), 2.8 [4H, m, -CH₂-N(CH₂)₂], 3.25 [4H, m, Ar-N(CH₂)₂], 4.18 (2H, s, -CH₂-N), 6.1 (1H, s, C₈H), 6.7-7.5 (7H, m, ArH) and 10.0 (1H, s, 7-OH exchangeable with D₂O).

The Mannich reaction of 1-phenylpiperazine on 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin: 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1.76 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (25 ml). To this boiling solution a mixture of paraformaldehyde (500 mg) and 1-phenylpiperazine (1.77 g, 0.011 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 6-8 h. It was concentrated and cooled when the product separated out. It was crystallised from ab. alcohol, yield of pure VII 1.8 g (72%).

7-Hydroxy-4-[2-(4-aryl-1-piperazinyl)-2-oxoethyl]coumarins IV: I (1 g) was heated with II (2 ml) in

an oil bath at 180-90° for 2 h. The gummy mass thus obtained was washed with 1 : 1 HCl (5 ml) and water and triturated with ethanol when the solid separated. The product was crystallised from ethanol (Table 2). IR (KBr) of IVa : 3250 (7-OH), 1720

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF IV

Compd.	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen %* Found (Calcd.)
IVa	H	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	264-66	68	7.65 (7.69)
IVb	2-OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	228-29	65	7.88 (7.40)
IVc	3-OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	284-85	63	7.41 (7.40)
IVd	4-OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	242-43	61	7.42 (7.40)
IVe	2-Cl	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄	247-48	69	7.00 (7.02)
IVf	3-Cl	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄	257-58	67	7.04 (7.02)
IVg	4-Cl	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄	252-58	65	7.05 (7.02)

* C and H analyses were found to be satisfactory.

(lactonic CO) and 1650 (-CON). PMR (DMSO-d₆) of IVa : 3.26 (4H, t, -CH₂N(CH₂)₂), 3.68 (4H, t, Ar-N(CH₂)₂), 4.0 (2H, s, 4-CH₂CON<), 6.12 (1H, s, C₈H) and 6.7-7.6 (8H, m, ArH).

Pharmacology :

The compounds were tested on mice (albino mice of Haffkin strain) for their expected CNS action in CMC suspension. All the compounds were found to be inactive even at the high dose of 900 mg/kg.

Inhibition of edema produced by carrageenin (0.1 ml of 1% Ca-carrageenin in normal saline, subcutaneous) in the hind paw of rats was measured by the standard method¹⁴. Phenylbutazone was used as the standard and % inhibition of the edema by the test compounds as well as by the standard as compared with the control was recorded (Table 1). Compounds III showed the activity during the first hour of administration. meta-Substitution of the N-phenyl ring of piperazine was found to be favourable and m-Cl was the most effective. Compounds IV showed no antiinflammatory activity.

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Synthesis and Pharmacological Activities of New 3-Phenyl-3(N,N-substituted aminomethyl)-2(3H)-benzofuranones

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3-PHENYL-2(3H)-benzofuranone, a γ -lactone, has been proved to be a potent pharmacophore for anticonvulsant activity¹. Some derivatives of 3-phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranone containing a basic moiety have been found to exhibit musculotropic, anaesthetic and antispasmodic properties²⁻⁴. Amethone, 3-phenyl-3(β -diethylaminoethyl)-2(3H)-benzofuranone is used against bronchial asthma and at the same time has a slight antihistaminic activity⁵. In spite of such valuable applications, enough work has not been done on such compounds. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to synthesize some 5, 6 or 7-substituted 3-phenyl-3(N,N-substituted aminomethyl)-2(3H)-benzofuranones and screen them for pharmacological properties. This communication deals with the results of this investigation.

Six different 3-phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranones (III) with a substituent at 5, 6 or 7-position have been synthesized by condensing mandelic acid (II) with appropriate phenols (I) in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid⁶⁻⁷.

Taking advantage of the labile nature of tertiary hydrogen at 3-position of 3-phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranone⁸⁻¹¹, each of these compounds (III) has been subjected to the Mannich condensation using para-formaldehyde and a secondary amine (IV). The Mannich bases, 5, 6 or 7-substituted-3-phenyl-3(N,N-substituted aminomethyl)-2(3H)-benzofuranones (V) thus obtained have been purified by recrystallisation from alcohol and characterized by their analytical, ir and pmr data.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer in nujol. PMR spectra were run on a Varian A-60 D instrument using TMS as the internal standard.